

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See *informed consent sheet*

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized transcript of recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	02/06/2021
Name of the interviewer	FRANCISCO VELASCO CABALLERO
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	RAFAEL SALGADO
Affiliation of the expert	MUNICIPALITY OF VALLADOLID
Position/Job description	WATCHDOG OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF VALLADOLID
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	
Area of expertise	WATCHDOG
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL AND URBAN

Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	In your opinion, what is the impact that increasing population movements from the countryside to cities have on local governments?
	Rural migrations are not a contemporary trend. They were very important during the 60s in the 20 th century, when the draining and emptying of small towns started (concerning Valladolid). Since then, the process and practice have been continuous. Today the phenomenon also affects (albeit mildly, the city of Valladolid) which, even though it is a large city, also loses population, moderately and gradually, towards the larger metropolises (especially Madrid)
1.1	<p><i>Do you know any public policies or best practices regarding the changing urban-rural relationships? Please consider practices in the following five areas:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Local responsibilities and public services.</i> - <i>Local financial arrangements.</i> - <i>Structure of local government.</i> - <i>Intergovernmental relations of local governments.</i> - <i>People’s participation in local decision-making.</i>
	There is a report from the Accounts Commission of Castilla – León’s Autonomous Community, where the various regional measures against depopulation are described and stated. Generally, none of these measures seem to be truly relevant in their effects against rural depopulation.
2	To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?

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	Usually, an increase in infrastructure does not seem relevant in the fight against depopulation. Infrastructures, especially those for transport, are generally very good and useful, but this does not mean that migration could be decreased or slowing down. A good case in this regard is the roads in the <i>Las Hurdes</i> region (between Salamanca and Cáceres) which are excellent, but it is not enough reason to prevent the intense depopulation process of the area. An exception and a very useful infrastructure could be digitization, in order to promote online and distance working in and from rural regions.
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LOCAL FINANCIAL ARRANGEMENTS

4	Do you know what approximate percentage of municipal income comes from municipal taxes, transfers (state, autonomous and provincial), and service fees?
	Approximately, in the case of the city of Valladolid, the Annual Property Tax (IBI) represents 35% of the municipal income; 30% comes from State Transfers; and 11% of fees derived from the provision of public services.
5	How do you value this income structure?
	It is a good income structure. Specifically, the high capacity of IBI (Annual Property Tax) has been fundamental during the economic crisis of 2008.
6	Do you consider that the municipality has good financing? 6.1. If the previous question is negative, where should the best financing come from: From municipal taxes, State /autonomous/ provincial transfers, services, or indebtedness?
	Currently, the Municipal Fiscal Autonomy is adequate. An increase in fiscal autonomy (further tax power) could be counterproductive, by fostering competition between municipalities, with negative results (as occurs currently in part with the vehicle Taxation, which is causing some small municipalities to lower each time the interest rates in order to attract owners).

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	<p>An increase in the tax burden, especially based on the IBI (Annual Property Tax) could be hardly acceptable. Today the IBI is already relatively high (1.000 Euros for an average home per year, in the city of Valladolid)</p> <p>The transfer financing can be improved in relation to some specific public services (such as social services) that are very expensive. At present, a good part of the social action is carried out by the Valladolid City Council through an agreement with the Community of Castilla y León. But this agreement does not cover the true cost of the service (barely reaches 40%), so more transfers are necessary (in this case, from the Autonomous Community)</p>
7	<p><i>Do you consider that municipal financing influences the migratory flow towards large cities?</i></p> <p><i>7.1. How? In which way?</i></p> <p><i>7.2. could you offer an example?</i></p>
	<p>In general, municipal funding does not influence migration. The municipal services and infrastructures are currently very good, with no shortcomings for the residents. Therefore, greater local financing could hardly offer better services and infrastructures and thus act against depopulation. Migrations, especially young people, do not occur due to a lack of public services or infrastructure, but rather because of the attractiveness and stimulus that larger cities such as Madrid have.</p>
8	<p>Does the aging of the population affect the budget of your municipality?</p>
	<p>Yes. Social action (which includes care for the elderly and /or dependents) is the largest specific expenditure in the city.</p>
9	<p>What other demographic changes affect the income structure?</p>
	<p>The gradual pace of population loss naturally affects the income structure. Although this loss in the case of Valladolid is moderate (it losses about 1.000 inhabitants per year, out of a current total of about 320,000 inhabitants).</p>
10	<p>In your opinion, does the municipality have a scattered population?</p>
	<p>The city of Valladolid, as such, does not have a dispersed population. But there are migrations (especially of young people) to the small municipalities that surround Valladolid.</p>
11	<p>To what extent does dispersion affect municipal income and expenditures?</p>

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	The city of Valladolid loses young taxpayers (those who go to the towns nearby Valladolid, where housing is cheaper)
12	In order to promote the development of rural municipalities, are more effective the public grants or unconditional financial transfers?
	Rural municipalities do not need better financing. Nor is there a great need to improve municipal services in rural areas. The depopulation problem is not directly related to services, but to other incentives from larger cities. Investing in more infrastructures and services for small numbers of the population (who already have sufficient services) is not entirely justified. Establishing schools in small municipalities for very few children is not justified, not even taking their best interest in mind, because they will be deprived of wider socialization.
13	In order to attract towards or retain the population in the rural municipalities, which municipal income structure do you consider would be more favorable?
	This question has been already answered indirectly above.

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

CURRENT TRANSFERS

14	How do you assess the amount of municipal income from current transfers?
	It has already been answered above that the current income structure is good, which also includes the general transfer regime.
15	From whom they receive these transfers? In what percentages?
	The unconditional transfers come from the State, in the percentage already mentioned above (30% of total income). Conditional transfers (for social action and transport) come from the Autonomous Community. The unconditional regional subsidies (PICA: Participation in the income of the Autonomous Community) are irrelevant.
15.1	Have they been constant during the last legislature?
	Transfers were reduced during the economic crisis that began in 2008. This is explained because state transfers (which are the most important) are based on taxes (such as income

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	<p>and VAT) that are highly sensitive to economic activity. As there was lower State revenue, transfers to municipalities were also reduced.</p> <p>Until now, the COVID-19 pandemic has not been noticed in municipal revenues, because State transfers are received in advance (on account). It will be next year, once the advances are adjusted when the State transfers will be predictably, much smaller.</p>
16	<p>Does the City Council receive current transfers from the Provincial Government?</p> <p>No. Only, the Provincial Council finances public services of the Provincial Council itself in the city of Valladolid (such as the operation or running of the Zorrilla Theater, which is property of the Provincial Council).</p> <p>Rather, it is the Valladolid City Council that provides some municipal services to some surrounding towns. This is the case of solid waste management in the municipalities near Valladolid, which is done by the Valladolid City's Council waste treatment plant (in exchange for a price, which small municipalities pay directly to the company hired by the Valladolid City Council).</p> <p>The same happened with the fire service until recently. In this case, the service was provided by the Valladolid City Council to the surrounding municipalities, although this service was paid by the Provincial Council for the smaller municipalities.</p>
17	<p>If the municipality is in a single province Autonomous Community: does it receive current transfers from the Community?</p> <p>It is not the case.</p>
18	<p>Do you consider the current transfers received by the City Council to be adequate?</p> <p>This question has already been answered in previous responses.</p>

Part C: Additional Country-Specific Questions

CAPITAL TRANSFERS

19	What is your opinion on the municipal income that comes from capital transfers?
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	<p>This income comes mainly from European Funds (especially ERDF funds). With these funds, the Smart City projects are being financed in a very important way. Currently, the city of Valladolid is not receiving these funds.</p> <p>For the future, the refinancing of the capital investment is envisaged through the EU Recovery Plan, after the end of the pandemic. Access to these funds is already prepared in the Department of Finance.</p>
20	What does the City Council dedicate capital transfers to?
	Basically, to the rehabilitation of slums and public works for sustainable mobility (especially infrastructures for bicycles).

CONDITIONAL GRANTS

21	How do you assess the conditional transfers that your Council receives?
	Overall, good. The European Union funds philosophy is the correct one.
22	To what extent are conditional subsidies channeled through the Provincial Plan for Constructions and Services?
	The Valladolid City Council does not receive subsidies from the Provincial Works and Services Plan.

PROVINCIAL SERVICES

23	Does the Provincial Government provide any service in the municipality? Which one?
	As mentioned earlier, the Zorrilla Theater (and therefore its activity) is owned by the municipality.
24	Do you think that the City Council could manage these services if it had better financing?
	Better financing is not necessary, the current one is fine. The problems are not so much in financial sufficiency as in spending efficiency, where there is much room for improvement. For example, right now the information on the costs of services does not have much relevance when it comes to making municipal decisions about those services.

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TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

25	Does your City Council receive technical assistance from the Provincial Government? And from the Autonomous Community?
	No.
26	Does the Provincial Government collaborate in municipal procedures, such as tax or payroll management?
	No.

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